

Adverse Outcome Pathways – Putting Regulatory Action in the High Seat or in Pandora’s Box?

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Abstract

Toxicity testing in the 21st Century was launched in 2007 as “the new toxicology” supported by computers and automation. Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) was expected to assess potential risks from an expanding number of chemicals or to consider a broader suite of effects than has commonly been considered in previous assessment efforts. At the same time, risk assessors faced increasing demands to assess more chemicals, with greater speed and accuracy, using fewer resources and lab animals. Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP) represent a dynamic approach to synthesizing complex information through acyclic graphs, offering a powerful framework for understanding the intricate connections between a molecular trigger (i.e. virous or chemical exposure) and health outcomes. How has the idea of AOPs evolved? How do we work with AOPs in Partnership for the Assessment of Risk from Chemicals (PARC) project?